

REPLACEMENT OF THE CONNECTION WITH MICROELEMENTS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF HYPOTHYROIDISM AND HYPERTHYROIDISM IN WOMEN OF REPRODUCTIVE AGE LIVING IN THE ARAL SEA REGION.

Masharipova Khulkar Qabulovna

Urganch State Medical Institute

<https://orcid.org/ORCID:0009-0006-9399-2257>

Annotation: The study of the causes of hypothyroidism and hyperthyroidism in women of reproductive age living in the Aral Sea region and the causes of microelement deficiency is relevant for the following reasons:

Impact on reproductive health: Thyroid hormone deficiency has a negative impact on pregnancy and childbirth in women. This condition can lead to premature and late births, complications and pathologies during pregnancy. It also has a negative impact on the health of infants.

Prevention and early detection of thyroid diseases in women are of great importance. This requires the improvement of medical services

Key words: microelements, the origin of hypothyroidism and hyperthyroidism, Thyroid gland.

ОРОЛБЎЙИДА ЯШОВЧИ РЕПРОДУКТИВ ЁШДАГИ АЁЛЛАРНИНГ ГИПОТИРЕОЗ ВА ГИПЕРТИРЕОЗ КЕЛИБ ЧИҚИШНИ МИКРОЭЛЕМЕНТЛАР БИЛАН БОҒЛИҚЛИГИНИ АСОСЛАШ.

Машарипова Хулкар Қабуловна

Урганч давлат тиббиёт институти

<https://orcid.org/ORCID:0009-0006-9399-2257>

Аннотация: Оролбўйида яшовчи репродуктив ёшдаги аёлларда гипотиреоз ва гипертиреоз келиб чиқишини микроэлементлар етишмовчилиги ҳолатларини ўрганиш куйидаги нуқталар билан долзарб ҳисобланади.

Репродуктив соғлиққа таъсири: Қалқонсимон без гормонлари етишмовчилиги аёлларда ҳомиладорлик ва туғруқ жараёнларига салбий таъсир кўрсатади. Бу ҳолат эрта ва кеч туғруқлар, ҳомиладорлик давридаги асоратлар ва патологияларга сабаб бўлиши мумкин. Шунингдек, чақалоқлар соғлиғига ҳам салбий таъсир кўрсатади.

Аёлларда қалқонсимон без касалликларининг олдини олиш ва эрта аниқлаш муҳим аҳамият касб этади. Бу эса тиббий хизматларни такомиллаштиришни талаб қилади

Калит сузлар: микроэлементлар, гипотиреоз ва гипертиреоз келиб чиқишини, Қалқонсимон без.

ЗАМЕНА СВЯЗИ С МИКРОЭЛЕМЕНТАМИ В ВОЗНИКНОВЕНИИ ГИПОТИРЕОЗА И ГИПЕРТИРЕОЗА У ЖЕНЩИН РЕПРОДУКТИВНОГО ВОЗРАСТА, ПРОЖИВАЮЩИХ В РЕГИОНЕ ПРИАРАЛЬЯ.

Машарипова Хулкар Қабуловна

Ургенчского государственного медицинского института

<https://orcid.org/ORCID:0009-0006-9399-2257>

Аннотация: Изучение причин гипотиреоза и гипертиреоза у женщин репродуктивного возраста, проживающих в Приаралье, а также причин дефицита микроэлементов актуально по следующим причинам.

Влияние на репродуктивное здоровье: Дефицит гормонов щитовидной железы оказывает негативное влияние на течение беременности и родов у женщин. Это состояние может привести к преждевременным и поздним родам, осложнениям и патологиям во время беременности, а также негативно сказывается на здоровье младенцев.

Профилактика и раннее выявление заболеваний щитовидной железы у женщин имеют большое значение, что требует совершенствования медицинской помощи.

Ключевые слова: микроэлементы, происхождение гипотиреоза и гипертиреоза, Щитовидная железа.

Relevance of the topic. The study of the causes of hypothyroidism and hyperthyroidism in women of reproductive age living in the Aral Sea region, as well as microelement deficiencies, is relevant for the following reasons.

The Aral Sea region is a region facing the problem of iodine deficiency. Iodine deficiency leads to thyroid dysfunction and hormonal imbalance. This can have serious consequences, especially for women of reproductive age.

Reproductive health effects: Thyroid hormone deficiency negatively affects pregnancy and childbirth in women. This condition can lead to premature and late births, complications and pathologies during pregnancy. It also negatively affects the health of babies.

Morphofunctional changes of the thyroid gland: Thyroid hormone deficiency causes changes in the morphological structure of the gland. Functional changes affect the production of thyroid hormones. Identifying these changes helps to choose treatment methods.

Prevention and early detection of thyroid diseases in women are of great importance. This requires improving medical services. It also indicates the need for scientific research devoted to these problems.

The purpose of the study: To substantiate the connection between microelements and the origin of hypothyroidism and hyperthyroidism in women of reproductive age living in the Aral Sea region and to optimize ways to correct it.

Results and their discussion: The study of the causes of hypothyroidism and hyperthyroidism in women of reproductive age living in the Aral Sea region due to microelement deficiency is relevant for the following reasons. This condition is of great scientific importance due to its impact on women's health and quality of life. Blood tests are used to assess changes in the amount of thyroid hormones,

as well as to study the clinical manifestations of the disease. This helps to correctly diagnose these pathological conditions. Based on scientifically based and modern approaches, measures are proposed for the prevention and effective treatment of thyroid diseases in women. The scientific significance of this research work is determined by the fact that it offers new scientific approaches to the diagnosis and treatment of thyroid dysfunction in women. Thyroid dysfunction - hypothyroidism and hyperthyroidism - is one of the most common problems among women. In these cases, the amount of the main thyroid hormones (thyroxine and triiodothyronine) exceeds or decreases above normal. This affects the physiological and psychological state of women, reducing their quality of life. Timely detection and treatment of hypothyroidism and hyperthyroidism are of great importance. For this, laboratory methods are the most effective means of assessing thyroid function. Blood tests measure the amount of the main hormones of the thyroid gland, that is, the level of hormonal activity. The high prevalence of thyroid diseases among women, their negative impact on quality of life and health, as well as the possibility of preventing the disease in cases that are detected in a timely manner and treated correctly, confirm the relevance of the topic. Therefore, the study and assessment of thyroid function in women using laboratory methods is of great scientific and practical importance. The main conditions leading to impaired thyroid function are hypothyroidism and hyperthyroidism. These diseases are more common in women. Laboratory methods can determine the functional state of the thyroid gland, that is, the concentration of hormones. Hypothyroidism is a condition in which the thyroid gland produces too little of the thyroid's main hormones (thyroxine and triiodothyronine). This can cause women to experience decreased physical and mental activity, dry skin, and weight gain. Blood tests are used for diagnosis and treatment. Hyperthyroidism is caused by an overactive thyroid gland. Blood tests are also the main diagnostic tool for hyperthyroidism.

Conclusion: Early detection of thyroid dysfunction and micronutrient deficiencies in the population living in the Aral Sea region, especially in women of reproductive age, will help prevent them.

Literature.

1. Машарипова, Х. К. (2022). ОБЩИЙ ПЕЧЕНОЧНЫЙ ПРОТОК У ДЕТЕЙ В ПОСТАТАЛЬНОМ ОНТОГЕНЕЗЕ. In *НАУЧНОЕ ОБОЗРЕНИЕ: АКТУАЛЬНЫЕ ВОПРОСЫ ТЕОРИИ И ПРАКТИКИ* (pp. 242-244).
2. Машарипова, Х. К., & Салаева, З. Ш. (2020). Часто болеющие дети в Хорезмском регионе. *European science*, (1 (50)), 66-69.
3. Аскарова, Р. И., Машарипова, Ш. С., Атажанов, Ш. З., Машарипова, Х. К., & Якубова, У. Б. (2019). ОСОБЕННОСТИ ТЕЧЕНИЯ БЕРЕМЕННОСТИ ЖЕНЩИН, БОЛЬНЫХ ТУБЕРКУЛЁЗОМ ОРГАНОВ ДЫХАНИЯ. In *International scientific review of the problems of natural sciences and medicine* (pp. 202-209).
4. Машарипова, Х. К. (2022). ОБЩИЙ ПЕЧЕНОЧНЫЙ ПРОТОК У ДЕТЕЙ В ПОСТАТАЛЬНОМ ОНТОГЕНЕЗЕ. In *НАУЧНОЕ ОБОЗРЕНИЕ: АКТУАЛЬНЫЕ ВОПРОСЫ ТЕОРИИ И ПРАКТИКИ* (pp. 242-244).
5. Машарипова, Х. К., & Машарипов, А. С. (2019). ЭКСТРАЦЕРЕБРАЛЬНАЯ ПАТОЛОГИЯ ДЫХАТЕЛЬНОЙ СИСТЕМЫ ПРИ ЧЕРЕПНО-МОЗГОВОЙ ТРАВМЕ. *Новый день в медицине*, (4), 207-211.
6. Машарипова, Х., Усманов, Р., & Ахмедова, С. (2020). Анатомическое строение печени детей разного возраста. *Журнал вестник врача*, 1(4), 36-42.